

An Assessment of Language Needs Analysis Of Arabic Language Students in Nigerian Universities: Quantitative Paradigm Method

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Abstract:

An effective curriculum design for a second or foreign language teaching cannot be achieved unless a preliminary work is done on the learner's need. In most cases, learners' needs are seen as the fundamental aspect of curriculum development that cannot be ignored. This study attempts to investigate the perspectives of Arabic students so as to give necessary information for the development of an Arabic language curriculum in Nigerian universities. Two hundred and eighty-eight (288) students were randomly chosen as the sample size from the population number of 1,148 students that cut across all the selected universities of this study. The instrument of the study was adopted from the Munby (1978) Communication Needs Processor which has seven parameters of language needs analysis. But this questionnaire focuses on two parameters only; the purposive and the instrumentality domains. Respondents weighed each item on a Likert-type scale. Statistical software package SPSS for Windows (Version 20) was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics analyses of frequencies, means and standard deviation of each item were analysed to determine the students' rate of their perceived Arabic language needs. The findings show that the main interest of students in learning Arabic because is for them to go to abroad for exchange program in Arab countries so as to have opportunity to work in Arab countries after graduation. They are of the opinion that Arabic- medium tertiary institutions course, vocational Arabic instruction, everyday Arabic and travel conversation, and Islamic Religious are their specific purposes of studying Arabic language. They also observed that speaking, reading, communicative language and written skills are needed to actualise their specific purposes. The research also gives the necessary suggestions on the effective development and implementation of Arabic language curriculum in other to meet up with needs of the students.

Keywords: Arabic language, Needs analysis, Curriculum, Nigerian universities

INTRODUCTION

Needs analysis (also known as needs assessment) has a vital role in the process of designing and carrying out any language course, its centrality has been acknowledged by several scholars and authors (Munby, 1978; Richterich and Chancerel, 1987; Hutchinson and Waters, 1987). Needs analysis has been defined by many researchers in different perspectives, but each of these definitions have many things in common and therefore, it generally refers to the activities that are involved in collecting information that will serve as the basis for developing a curriculum that will meet the needs of a particular group of students. Some researchers believe that needs analysis is the first step in course design and it provides validity and relevancy for all subsequent course design activities (Johns, 2008).

Needs analysis was first established in the mid-1970s (West, 1998). It was seen as mainly concerned with linguistic and register analysis, as Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) suggest, needs were seen as discrete language items of grammar and vocabulary. The establishment of Munby's Communicative Syllabus Design (1978) needs analysis moved towards placing the learner's purposes in the central position within the framework of needs analysis. Consequently, the notion of target needs became paramount and research proved that function and situation were also fundamental. (Songhori, 2008). Jordan (1994) indicates that the main two approaches in needs analysis are the Target-Situation Analysis and the Present-Situation Analysis. The target situation analysis tries to establish what the learners are expected to be like at the end of the language course, while present situation analysis attempts to identify what they are like at the beginning of course.

The Target-Situation Analysis model is an offshoot of Munby's (1978) model of the Communication Needs Process. This model contains a detailed set of procedures for discovering

target situation needs. It is based on analyzing language communication in the target situation in order to provide a communicative needs profile for a specified group of learners. The Communication Needs Process profile seeks to present a valid specification of the skills and linguistic forms that a group of learners needs in the intended target situation. The Communication Needs Process model contained nine components (e.g. participant, purposive domain, setting, interaction, instrumentality, dialect, target level, communicative event, and communicative key). Each component asks questions about the use of the target language in order to identify learners' real world communicative requirements.

However, this study wishes to explore the perspectives of the Arabic language students to establish the necessary language needs of the students learning Arabic language in Nigerian institutions of higher learning. The outcome will be used as an input to prepare the intended group of learners for their intended use of the target language through converting the needs profile into a communicative competence specification that will be presented in a form of a curriculum for the program.

Statement of problem

The nature of Nigeria as a multi religious country and her linguistically diverse regions with different ethnic background and cultural diversity coupled with the affiliation of Arabic language with Islamic religion has an adverse effect on the development of Arabic language in Nigerian system of education.

Although, Arabic is viewed in the NPE as one of the selected languages for international communication and discourse, however, Arabic language being a language of liturgy in which the Islamic scripture (al –Quran) was revealed could not have the opportunity of universal acceptance of all Nigerian citizens because of the unending rivalry between Islam whose vehicle is believed to be Arabic language and Christianity that is believed to be the religion of European missionaries and Colonial masters. As a result of this, according to Oderinde (2003: 13) “Islam became the anathema, Arabic language, the language of Islam, is equally destined for hostility and the guillotine” Among the linguistic qualities of Arabic language as highlighted by Oderinde (2003) is the fact that the language is one of the normative and wide spoken languages

in the world. And it is also an international language for communication, politics, and diplomacy.

However, despite the fact that many researchers have worked on the development of the language in Nigeria and outlined the problems militating against its development, yet there still a need to recognise and accept it as an international language in Nigeria. This research argues that a systematic and highly empirical finding is needed in order to get to the root of these problems by investigating the students' perspectives of learning the language so much that all the linguistic qualities associated with Arabic language can be integrated into its curriculum for the effective teaching and learning of the language in Nigerian institutions of higher education

Purpose of the study

Needs analysis is a complex process which has to take into account what learners need to do in the target situation – i.e. language use, and “learning needs”, what learners need to do in order to learn – i.e. language learning. In a more modern view, we should not only take into account “target needs” and “learning needs” – i.e. objective needs – but also learners' subjective needs, that is, their affective needs, such as their interests, wishes, expectations and preferences. Therefore, in order to put all these factors into consideration, the main purpose of this study is to verify the perspective of Arabic language students' needs so as to determine their specific purposes of studying Arabic language with the necessary language skill needed for their specific purposes.

Research Questions

Therefore, this study wishes to answer the following research questions:

- ❖ How do university students perceive their interest of studying Arabic language?
- ❖ How do university students perceive their specific purposes of learning Arabic language?
- ❖ How do university students perceive the necessary language skills needed for their Arabic language specific purposes?
- ❖ How do university students rate the availability of language teaching materials in their schools?

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The population of this study comprised all the university students of Arabic language in Nigeria and the target population were all the Arabic students of the six (6) selected universities in Nigeria. However, since it was not possible to reach all the universities' students studying Arabic in Nigeria due to logistic constrains. The study sampled the selected universities based on geo-political zones.

Glesne (1998) argues that the number of sites for a study depends on the research interest and what the researcher wants to learn in the process. In order to ensure a fair representation of the target population in terms of ownership/proprietorship of the universities in Nigeria, the selected universities were based on Federal, State and Private owned universities

Therefore, the respondents for this study were chosen from six (6) universities by putting into consideration the ownership and the location of the universities within the four geo-political zones. The Federal universities were University of Maiduguri, Borno State (North-East), Bayero University Kano, Kano State (North-West), University of Ilorin, Kwara State (North-Central) and University of Ibadan, Oyo State (South-West). The State University was Lagos State University (South-West) while the private university was Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State (North-Central). The information gathered from the Arabic departments of these universities showed that the total number of students studying Arabic language as a course in all the selected universities during 2020/2021 academic session was one thousand one hundred and forty-eight (1,148) students.

As a result of this, two hundred and eighty- eight (288) students were randomly chosen as the sample size from the population number of 1,148 students, and it cut across all the selected universities of this study. This satisfied the sample size criteria of Krejcie, & Morgan (1970). The table shown below was adopted from Krejcie & Morgan (1970) and helps the researcher to determine with 95 per cent certainty of what the results would have been if the entire population had been surveyed. This sampling is also in line with Cohen's Statistical Power Analysis (1998)

Table 3.1

Determining the Random Sample Size from a Determined Population

If your Population is:	Then your random Sample size should be
1,100	285
1,148	288
1,200	291
1,300	297
1,400	302
1,500	306
1,600	310

Sample Size for Research Activities Adopted from Krejcie & Morgan, (1970)

Research Instrument

The questionnaire was modified from the Munby (1978) Communication Needs Processor which has seven parameters of language needs analysis, but this questionnaire focuses on two parameters only; The purposive domain and the instrumentality.

- The Purposive domain establishes the type of second language needs and the purpose that the target language will be used for at the end of the course,
- The Instrumentality specifies the medium and skills, i.e., whether the language to be used is written, spoken, reading or listen.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The survey of the twenty-five (25) items questionnaire of the Language Needs Analysis (LNA) for the Arabic Language Students of Higher Institutions was distributed to the respondents after permission has been granted by the HODs with the consent of the respondents. The respondents were randomly selected and asked to weigh each item on a Likert- type scale. Statistical software package SPSS for Windows (Version 20) was used for data analysis. The frequency of the

demographic data: age, sex, educational background, year of study, religion, state of origin was analysed. Descriptive statistics analyses of frequencies, means and standard deviation of each item were used to determine the students' rate of their perceived Arabic needs.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The questionnaire was divided into five parts. The first part of the Students' Questionnaire gathers the students' demographic information, including gender, year of study, name of the Institution, religion, Arabic background, Arabic certificate obtained before the University programme, present level of proficiency in Arabic language and area of interest in Arabic courses. The data was calculated and analyzed by descriptive statistics using frequency and percentages to report a summary of the characteristics of the demographic data. The remaining four parts of the questionnaire were analyzed by the frequencies, means and standard deviation of the students' perspectives on their Arabic language needs, which include their interest in Arabic language, specific purposes of learning Arabic language, necessary skills needed for their specific purposes and availability of language teaching facilities in their various schools. The analyses of the Arabic students' perceived needs are as follows:

Demographic Information of the Respondents

Table 1 Demographic Information on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	214	74.3(%)
Female	74	25.7 (%)

The total number of the participants was 288. 214 (74.3%) were male, and 74 (25.7%) were female. The number of male participants was greater than female in this study. Moreover, males always outnumber the females in the entire Arabic Departments understudy and there is no female student in some Arabic Departments. This shows that there is a wide disparity in the gender of Arabic language students in Nigerian Universities.

Table 2. Demographic Information on Age

Age of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25	65	22.6(%)
26-30	176	61.1(%)
30 above	47	16.3 (%)

Age of Respondents

As showed in Table below, 65 students (22.6 %) were between the ages of 18 and 25years, 176 students (61.1 %) are between the ages of 26 and 30years, while the remaining 47 students (16.3 %) are above 30 years of age. This is a clear manifestation that the long process involved in the acquisition of Arabic language in Nigeria always make the Arabic students to spend more duration in the process of their study more than any other students in Nigeria system of education because the majority of Nigeria University students always fall between the age limit of 18 and 25 years.

Table 3.Demographic Information on Year of Study

Year of Study	Frequency	Percentage (%)
100level	31	10.8(%)
200level	67	23.3(%)
300level	119	41.3(%)
400level	71	24.7(%)

Year of Study

The table indicates that there is a decline in the number of Arabic students across their year of studies. Students in year three were the highest with 119 (41.3 %) followed by the students in year four 71 (24.7 %), the number of students in year two were 67 (23.3 %) while the first year students had the lowest number of 31(10.8 %). Although the respondents were chosen through random sampling but the number of respondents according to their year of study still shows that

there is a down trend in the Arabic students' intakes over the years. This has also been established in the Arabic students' statistics obtained from various Universities under study.

Table 4. Demographic Information on Institutions

Institutions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lagos State University	24	8.3(%)
University of Ilorin	32	11.1%
Bayero University Kano	96	33.3(%)
University of Ibadan	48	16.7(%)
University of Maiduguri	67	23.3(%)
Al-Hikmah University	21	7.3(%)

Institutions

Table shows that the number of Arabic students in each University was put into consideration in order to obtain the random sample size of this study. The universities with higher number of students have more participants in the study than the University with low students. Therefore, Bayero University, Kano had the highest number of participants 96 (33.3 %), the number of participants from University of Maiduguri was 67 (23.3 %) and University of Ilorin had 32 (11.1 %) participants, 48 (16.7 %) participants were chosen from University of Ibadan, the number of participants from Lagos State University was 24 (8.3%) while Al-Hikmah University had 21 (7.3 %) participants.

Table 5. Demographic Information on Religion

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Islam	288	100(%)
Christianity	-	-
Others	-	-

Religion

As it showed in the table below, all the students that participated in the study are Muslims 288 (100%). There was no any indication whatsoever to show that any Nigeria University has

Christian or other believer except Muslims in her Arabic Department. This is a clear indication that despite the status of Arabic language in BMAS as a foreign language, Arabic language is still perceived in Nigeria as a language that can be studied by Muslims only.

Table 6.Demographic Information on Arabic Background

Arabic Background,	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	273	94.8(%)
No	15	5.2(%)

Arabic Background

The table below showed that many of the participants have background in the study of Arabic language before joining the university. 273 (94.8 %) of the participants indicated that they have acquired the study of the language before their university education. While 15 (5.2 %) participants do not have any background in Arabic language before joining the University.

Table 7. Demographic Information on Arabic Certificate

Arabic Certificate	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No Arabic Certificate	15	5.2(%)
Idadiya	34	11.8(%)
Thanawiyah	143	49.7(%)
Diploma	96	33.3(%)

Arabic Certificate

The significant of private Arabic schools as the provider of students for Arabic Departments in Nigeria University has clearly manifested in this study. Table 4.13 shows that 143 (49.7 %) of the participants said that they have graduated from Arabic school with (thanawiyah) secondary school certificate, 34 (11.8%) participants have (idadiya) primary school certificate and 96 (33.3 %) participants have diploma certificate from their various Arabic schools. However, only 15 (5.2 %) participants indicated that they did not pass through any Arabic school before getting admission into the University to read Arabic language.

Table 8. Demographic Information on Arabic Proficiency

Level of Proficiency	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Good	73	25.3(%)
Good	130	45.1(%)
Average	68	23.6(%)
Low	12	4.2(%)
Very Low	5	1.7(%)

Level of Proficiency

Many of the Arabic students as it is showed in table 4.14 indicate that their proficiency level of Arabic language is very high. 130 (45.1 %) said that their proficiency level is very good, 73 (25.3 %) said they have good proficiency of Arabic language, 68 (23.6 %) indicated that their Arabic proficiency is average, 12 (4.2 %) participants have low proficiency in Arabic language while only 5 (1.7 %) participants have a very low proficiency of Arabic language. It also pertinent to say that those who have low proficiency in the language are those that do not have any background of Arabic language and do not passed through any Arabic schools.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Students’ Perception on Arabic Language Needs

The purpose of this section is to assess the students’ perspectives on their language needs and also to determine the specific skills that can lead to the achievements of their aims and objectives in studying Arabic language in the university. This section is divided into four parts with 20 items. The first part has 7 items that assessed the students’ interest in taking Arabic language as a course of study. The overall frequency, mean scores and standard deviation for each of the items were calculated based on a scale from "1" (not important) to "6" (very important).

The second part explored the students’ perspectives on their specific purposes of learning Arabic language. It has four items for four specific purposes of learning Arabic language in the University, the frequency, mean score and standard deviation of each specific purposes were calculated based on a scale from "1" (not at all useful) to "6"(very useful). The third part found out the perspective of the students on the necessary skills needed for their specific purposes, the frequency, mean score and standard deviation of each of the four skills were calculated, in the first item, the students were asked to choose between the four basic language skills according to their order of importance towards the specific goals of the students while the remaining 3 items were based on a scale from "1" (not at all important) to "6"(very important).

The fourth part investigated the perspective of the students on the availability of the necessary teaching materials in their Arabic Departments. The frequency, mean score and standard deviation of the five teaching materials were calculated based on a scale from "1" (strongly disagreed) to "6"(strongly agree). The statistical tables and analysis of each sub-section are discussed below.

Table 9.Interest in Learning Arabic Language

Item	Strongly Disagree (n)	Somewhat Disagree (n)	Slightly Disagree (n)	Slightly Agree (n)	Somewhat Agree (n)	Strongly Agree (n)	M	SD
I am interested in doing a study abroad in an Arabic speaking country while I am still a student in the university.	7.6% (22)	2.1% (6)	2.4% (7)	8% (23)	24% (69)	55.9% (161)	5.0	1.6

I have a goal to get a job which requires Arabic language after I graduated from the university.	1.7% (5)	1.7% (5)	2.4% (7)	10.4% (30)	24.7% (71)	59% (170)	5.3	1.0
I have a goal to work in Arabic country after graduating from the university	0.3% (1)	2.4% (7)	2.8% (8)	13.9% (40)	27.8% (80)	51.4% (148)	5.2	1.1
I want to learn Arabic to be more educated	29.2% (85)	-	-	2.4% (7)	21.5% (62)	75.5% (218)	5.7	.56
I want to learn Arabic for better understanding of Islamic religion.	-	-	-	3.8% (11)	20.1% (58)	76% (219)	5.7	.52
I believe learning Arabic is important to get a good job after graduating	-	2.8% (8)	3.1% (9)	13.5% (39)	20.1% (58)	52.8% (152)	4.9	1.5
If the university has given me another course instead of Arabic I would have loved to take it	34.7% (100)	11.5% (33)	9.4% (27)	14.6% (42)	9.7% (28)	20.1% (58)	3.1	2.0

Interest in Learning Arabic Language

The findings in the table below show that majority of the students 253 (81%) (M=5.0, SD=1.6) are highly interested in learning Arabic. This is because they have inspiration of going to abroad for exchange program in Arab countries. It is also noted that more than average of the students 268 (96.1%) (M=5.3, SD=1.0) have a goal to work in Arab countries after graduation. However, it is pertinent to note that the Arab countries are not putting much effort in encouraging the non-speakers to have much interest in learning their language as it is done by British and French

countries. The nonchalant attitude of the native speakers in the development of the language is in line with the views of (Oderinde, 2007 & Oloyede, 2003). Oderinde (2007) is of the view that the involvement of Arab Nation in the development of Arabic Language in non-Arab speaking countries is not encouraging. He recommends that the Arab Governments directly or through ALESCO (Arab League Educational, Social and Cultural Organisation) should give financial assistance to the countries where Arabic is taught due to the fact that their language is being promoted and not just for the propagation of Islam.

Oloyede (2003) asserts that Arab's efforts in the promotion of Arabic language are not yielding maximal dividends probably due to lack of net-working among the Arab-nations, and absence of strategic intervention in Arabic Language-promotion in non-Arab areas of the world. He suggests the establishment of a truly International academy for the study and promotion of Arabic Language. He maintains that such Academy, if jointly promoted by Arab-nations of the world, would create acceptable Arabic terms and terminologies for contemporary inventions and scientific concepts.

Furthermore, the study also showed that there is no much difference between the students who have interest in the course and those who prefer to take another course. The item that states "if the university has given me another course instead of Arabic i would have loved to take it" showed that 160 (55.6%) students disagreed that they will take another course even if they were given. And 128 (44.4%) students showed interest in taking another course rather than Arabic language. This is an indication that the number of students who have interest in Arabic and students who do not have interest in it is almost the same. This shows that Arabic lecturers still need to put more effort to encourage students in learning the course.

Many researchers believe that the attitudes and conducts of a teacher to his student will make an everlasting impression in the students' behavior and will also influence his interest in the course (Pianta, 1999; Watson, 2003).

Richardson (1996) opines that effective attitudes can build good relationships and mutual respect and trust between teachers and students. This view was also acknowledged by Gourneau, (2002) who asserts that there is potential in every student and teacher's attitude which can leave lasting impressions.

He discusses five frequently attitudes and actions of an effective teacher which include sincere caring, kindness, benevolent of the teacher to the students, helpful hand and meaningful provision of learning experience to the students with ‘enthusiasm for stimulating the students’ creativity.

Table 10. Perspective on Specific Purposes of Learning Arabic Language

Item	Not at all Useful (n)	Not so Useful (n)	Slightly Useful (n)	A little Useful (n)	Somewhat Useful (n)	Very Useful (n)	M	SD
How useful do you feel Arabic instruction (Arabic needed for Arabic-medium tertiary institutions courses) is needed for your future Arabic language needs?	2.4% (7)	2.4% (7)	3.1% (9)	4.2% (12)	21.2% (61)	66.7% (192)	5.3	1.1
How useful do you feel vocational Arabic instruction is needed for your future Arabic language needs?	0.3% (1)	0.7% (2)	9% (14)	6.6% (19)	26.4% (76)	61.1% (176)	5.4	.90
How useful do you feel general Arabic instruction (everyday conversational Arabic and travel Arabic) is needed	3% (1)	1.0% (3)	1.7% (5)	5.2% (15)	16.3% (47)	75.3% (217)	5.6	.80

for your future Arabic language needs?

How useful do you feel Islamic religious Arabic instruction is needed for your future Arabic?	1.4% (4)	5.2% (15)	3.1% (9)	9.7% (28)	80.2% (231)	5.6	.92
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Specific Purposes of Learning Arabic Language

Students are of the opinion that Arabic should be studied for specific purposes. They agreed that the following specific purposes are needed for their Arabic language needs: Arabic- medium tertiary institutions course, vocational Arabic instruction, everyday Arabic and travel conversation, and Islamic Religious Arabic instruction. Students viewed everyday Arabic conversation and Islamic Religious Arabic as the most needed instruction for their future needs. This confirms the view of Muhammad, (1998) who contends that Arabic for specific purposes is an inevitable development and should be introduced to the field of teaching Arabic as a foreign language. However, students have much believed in Arabic language as a prerequisite toward the understanding of Islamic religion. This manifested in their choice of ‘Islamic Religious Arabic’ as a course that necessitates the learning of Arabic language.

Table 11. Perspective on the Necessary Skills Needed for Future Purposes

Items	Reading (n)	Writing (n)	Speaking (n)	Listening (n)	M	SD
Which of the following skills do you feel would be most useful to learn and practice for improving your overall Arabic ability as far as your specific purpose is	22.2% (64)	9.7% (28)	58% (167)	10% (29)	2.60	.94

concern?

Table 11b. Perspective on the Necessary Skills Needed for Future Purposes

Item	Not all Importan t (n)	Somewh at not Importan t (n)	Slightly not Importan t (n)	Slightly Importan t (n)	Somewh at Importan t (n)	Very Importan t (n)	M	SD
How important is to have vocabulary practice in Arabic classes	7% (2)	4.2% (12)	-	6.2% (18)	14.6% (42)	74.3% (214)	5.6	.84
How important is to have written practice in Arabic classes	-	3% (1)	1.7% (5)	3.5% (10)	20.5% (59)	74% (213)	5.6	.67
How important is to have communicative language practice in Arabic classes	3% (1)	3% (1)	1.0% (3)	5.2% (15)	9.4% (27)	83.7% (241)	5.7	.69

Necessary Skills Needed for Students’ Future Purposes

More so, students were of the opinion that the most important language skill needed to help them in actualizing their Arabic specific purpose is the speaking skills, followed by reading and they also gave much priority to communicative language and written practices in Arabic classes. This is in line with the present trend in the teaching and learning of modern language that gives much emphasis to communicative competency as the best methodology of teaching modern language (Fonicchairo & Bono, 1973; Krashen, 1981; Savignon, 1983; Chomsky, 1996; Burke, 2006, 2007).

Despite the students’ view in communicative competence as the best means of acquiring Arabic language, it should be noted that the methodologies of teaching and learning Arabic language in Nigeria and many non-Arab countries are rote learning, grammar translation and memorization (Abd ul- Halim, 1982; Ta’mah, 1990; Oseni, 1991; Lawal, 1991; Ismail, 1993; Bidmos, 1996; Oladosu,2001; Haron, 2012).

Table 12.Perspectives on the Availability of Teaching Materi

Item	Strongly Disagree (n)	Somewhat Disagree (n)	Slightly Disagree (n)	Slightly Agree (n)	Somewhat Agree (n)	Strongly Agree (n)	M	SD
There are enough computers in my Department that we use for our Arabic courses	26.0% (75)	62.2% (179)	10.1% (29)	-	1.0% (3)	7% (2)	1.90	.74
There are enough audio/ visual aids in my Department that we use for our Arabic courses	20.5% (59)	64.6% (186)	14.9% (43)	-	-	-	1.94	.59
My Department has a language laboratory that we use for our Arabic courses	20.5% (59)	64.6% (186)	14.9% (43)	-	-	-	1.86	.71
We have access to enough Arabic newspapers and magazines in our Department	33.0% (95)	47.6% (137)	19.4% (56)	-	-	-	1.82	.64

My Department	29.2% (85)	52.4%	17.0%	1.0%	-	-	1.90	.72
has organised		(151)	(49)	(3)				
different trips								
and field works								
for us that gave								
us the								
opportunity to								
meet the Arabs								
and								
communicate								
with them in								
Arabic language								

Availability of the Necessary Language Teaching Material

All the students 288 (100%) firmly rejected the statement that their teachers use the modern teaching facilities in the class such as audio visual aids, language laboratory, projectors, newspaper and magazine. However, it is pertinent to say that all these teaching facilities are mentioned in the Benchmark Minimum Standard as indispensable tools to the effective teaching and learning of Arabic language in Nigerian universities. Thus, the findings confirmed the earlier studies carried out by different researchers on the non-availability of Arabic language teaching materials in Nigerian schools (Oseni, 1991: Bidmos, 1992: Oladosu, 2001: Oloyede, 2012).

Bidmos (1992), in his critical assessment of the status of Arabic language within the Universal Basic Education (UBE), concludes that Arabic language has not been properly absorbed into the education system of the country. He notes that the mere appearance of the language in the public schools is not enough to ensure its perfect absorption into the public schools' system. He lays emphasis on some of the integral aspects of learning modern language that are still lacking in the schools, such as modern language equipment and also provision of special trained teachers of the language. The same conclusion was put forward by Oladosu (2001) in his appraisal of the problems militating against the development of Arabic language in the UBE system in Nigeria.

Zuber-Skerritt (1994) asserts that misconceptions about the use of technology limit innovation and threaten teachers' job and security. Therefore, teachers need to get themselves familiar with the technology of teaching modern language with computers. They need to

abandon the notion of “old habit dies hard” that continues to indulge them in the adoption of the traditional methods of teaching foreign language.

Kuang-wu Lee, (2000) concludes that modern technologies will never substitute teachers but will offer new opportunities for better language practice. They may actually make the process of language learning significantly richer and play a key role in the reform of a country's educational system.

Oloyede, (2003) argues that Information Computer Technology (ICT) has broken so many grounds to provide ‘ease and comfort’ for humanity. In the delivery of the mandate of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Oloyede laments that, it will be wasteful to neglect or failure not to take full advantage of such devices, which facilitate the tasks of a contemporary world. He highlights some of the Arabic software that can aid the teaching and learning Arabic language, they include; Turath-Arabic as a second language software and Al-Qamusun natiq. These two softwares according to Oloyede are very useful in getting non-native speaker of Arabic closer to the native speakers

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

The analyses of the Arabic students’ perceived needs shows that the total number of the participants was 288. 214 (74.3%) were male, and 74 (25.7%) were female. This is a clear manifestation that Arabic class is always dominated by male students. The long process involved in the acquisition of Arabic language in Nigeria is a result of the fact that many Arabic students always pass through the modern Arabic schools after their secondary before gaining admission into the university. This makes them to spend more duration in the process of their study more than any other students in Nigeria system of education because the majority of Nigeria University students always fall between the age limit of 18 and 25 years while the age of the majority of Arabic students is between 25 and 30years.

Moreover, the influence of Islamic religion on the study of Arabic language is clearly manifested in this research in which the universities in the Northern part of the country that are predominantly dominated by Muslims have large number Arabic students in their departments while the admission in the South- West universities is very precarious and abysmal. It is also noted that Arabic is not offered in any university in both South-South and South East of the country that are dominated by the Christians. As it showed in the research, all the students that

participated in the study are Muslims 288 (100%). There was no any indication whatsoever to show that any Nigeria University has Christian or other believer except Muslims in her Arabic department. Furthermore, the finding of the research shows that majority of the students 253 (81%) ($M=5.0$, $SD=1.6$) are highly interested in learning Arabic language. This is because they have inspiration of going to abroad for exchange program in Arab Countries Arabic- medium tertiary institutions course, vocational Arabic instruction, everyday Arabic and travel conversation, and Islamic Religious Arabic instruction. the most important language skill needed to help them in actualizing their Arabic specific purpose is the speaking skills, followed by reading and they also gave much priority to communicative language and written practices in Arabic classes.

However, the students rejected affirmatively that their teachers use any modern teaching facilities in the class such as audio visual aids, language laboratory, projectors, newspaper and magazine. All these are clear indications of the weaknesses of the Arabic curriculum in Nigerian Universities.

CONCLUSION

Arabic education in Nigeria is on the verge of collapse while Nigerian education system in general is faced with multifaceted challenges resulting from the myriad of issues such as political, social and economic instability. It is therefore pertinent to say that with the amazing rates of change in the world today, there is need for readjustment in Nigeria educational curriculum from time to time to meet the societal demands of the global economy.

This study believes that a dynamic and progressive nation demands an education that will create sincerity and good life for its members. Therefore, to adjust to the changing time there has to be constant evaluation of the entire existing curriculum to ensure that they still meet the needs of the times.

This study has exposed the salient issues militating against the development of Arabic language in Nigeria institution of higher learning. It also establishes the fact that the teaching of Arabic language in Nigerian institutions has not been tailored towards the goals of the National Policy on Education and the curriculum designed for the programme fails to achieve the aims and

objectives of the teaching and learning Arabic language in Nigerian institutions of higher learning.

Therefore, there is need for total repackage of the entire curriculum of Arabic language at all levels of Nigerian system of education. The suggestions and recommendations provided in this study will go a long way in finding an everlasting solution to the integration of Arabic programme into the Universal Basic Education system. The findings of this study also give an avenue for all the stakeholders in education agencies to map out the strategy for proper evaluation of all the courses offered in Nigerian institutions.

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